

NUSCOPE: Northeastern University Spectroscopy COrrrelation Processing Engine

NUSCOPE software is written in Java with a Swing graphical user interface by Steven Lustig (contact: s.lustig@northeastern.edu). This software is intended to be an experiment-analysis-to-manuscript-preparation workbench. It features capabilities: to read simple+universal file formats for spectrum data, to combine time series of single spectrum files into a single shig data table file, integrate multiple peaks in a single spectrum, and multiple peaks in a shig spectrum set, to interleave integrations of polarized spectra, to implement data filtering algorithms on shig spectrum sets, to compute and save several 2D correlation function plots, and to sort any number of spectral events into a single overall timeline following Noda's rules. It is the intent that the function plots are suitable for publication.